

Malice: The Metaworld of Book and Graphic (Comic) Novel

Noel Kok Hwee CHIA EdD, FCP, FCoT, FCollIP
Honorary Advisor
Reading Specialists' Association
Singapore

ABSTRACT

The concept of multiverse can be quite daunting to readers who do not have the slightest idea of what it is. There are already many hypotheses derived from theoretical physics to explain the possible existence of more than just our universe alone. The aim of this short paper is to take readers on a learning journey into the least explored metaworld of book and graphic (comic) novel combined into one, such as Malice (2009) written by Chris Woodling. Malice is the first of the duology; the other book is Havoc (2010). The term metaworld is also known by other terms such as the realms of fantasy in English literature or multiverse (or metaverse) in quantum physics. The author attempts to use Malice – the fictive metaworld – to explain the parallel similarities between the literary metaworld and the hypothetical multiverse or metaverse (both terms are used interchangeably throughout this paper). More importantly, the author wants to highlight that fantasy such as Malice (or Havoc) can provide an alternative explanation via literary channel to help our students appreciate the complexity of theoretical physics of multiverse.

Key words: *metaverse, metaworld, multiverse, multiworld, universe,*

INTRODUCTION

This planet Earth, where we are living today, may not be the only world or this universe is not the only one that exists. In other words, our world could be just one of an infinite number of worlds. I refer to use the term *metaworlds*. Scientists prefer to use the term *universes* (instead of *worlds*) that make up what has been termed as a *multiverse*. So, what is this *multiverse* (or *multiworld*¹) that we currently understand today?

Back in 1952, Erwin Schrodinger (b.1887-d.1961), a Nobel Prize-winning Austrian physicist, claimed that his mathematical equations seemed to describe several different histories but, he argued, that these equations were "not alternatives, but all really happen simultaneously" (cited in Deutsch, 2011, p.310). This is the earliest known reference to the multiverse (see Deutsch, 2011, for detail). This is an interesting observation from the mathematical (scientific) point of view. The American philosopher and psychologist, William James (b.1842-d.1910), used the term *multiverse* in 1895, but in a different context, to mean "[V]isible nature is all plasticity and indifference, a multiverse, as one might call it, and not a universe" (James, 1895, p.10).

¹ The terms multiverse and multiworld will be used interchangeably throughout this paper to mean the same thing. Personally, I would refer a multiverse to a global context containing many universes, while a multiworld contains many parallel worlds related to each other located within a universe.

Definition of Multiverse

Next, what do we understand by the term *multiverse* (or *multiworld* if that is the other term one prefers)? What does it mean exactly? According to the Wikipedia (2014), multiverse (or multiworld) is defined as "the hypothetical set of possible universes/*worlds*, including the universe/*world* where we *dwell*. Together, these universes/*worlds* comprise everything that exists: the entirety of space, time, matter, energy, and the physical laws and constants that *define or* describe them" (para.1; words in italic are the author's own). Within the multiverse/multiworld are various universes/*worlds* known as "parallel universes/*worlds*", "other universes/*worlds*" or "alternative universes/*worlds*".

The Scientific Hypotheses behind the Concept of Multiverse/Multiworld

Though the concept of multiverse/multiworld may stretch its credulity, there is still some good physics (*theoretical physics*, to be more precise) behind it. In fact, there are currently several hypotheses of theoretical physics that have independently pointed to the possible existence of multiverse (or *metaverse*) which, some experts believe, are likely than not, hidden worlds away from ours.

According to Moskowitz (2012), there are five most plausible scientific theories (or hypotheses to be more accurate, although mathematically, it is possible to prove the existence of a multiverse) that can explain the existence of a multiworld:

The Hypothesis of Infinite Universes

Nobody can be a hundred percent certain about what the shape and size of space-time is, but most likely, it seems to be flat rather than spherical or donut-shape as what some people believe, and that it probably stretches out infinitely. The vast space-time beyond that distance of 13.7 billion light-years since the day of the Big Bang (if one believes that it did happen) can be regarded as a separate universe of its own. In this way, a multitude of universes (or multiverse) exists next to each other in a giant patchwork quilt of universes (see Greene, 2011, for detail). If the space-time can go on indefinitely, there will be at some point when it keeps repeating itself since there is a finite number of ways particles can be arranged in the context of space-time. This means there will be an infinite number of universes!

In other words, if we were to look hard and far enough, we might encounter other versions of ourselves. In fact, there will be an infinite number of versions of ourselves. Some of our selves will be performing exactly what we are doing right now; others of our selves will be doing different tasks (e.g., cooking a sumptuous meal when in fact, we hardly know how to cook in our world here!). There are still others of ourselves in those infinite universes that "will have made vastly different career and life choices" (Moskowitz, 2012, para.5). These other selves of us are our avatars or doppelgangers.

The Hypothesis of Bubble Universes

According to the Theory of Eternal Inflation, first proposed by Vilenkin (1983), as a result of the Big Bang that happened around 13.7 billion years (that would be 13.7 billion light-years) ago, multiple universes are created by infinitely extending space-time and hence, other universes could arise from this "eternal inflation." The word *inflation* offers the notion that the universe expanded rapidly after the Big Bang, like an inflating balloon. Some pockets of space stop inflating, while there are still other regions that continue to inflate. As a result, this hypothetical phenomenon has given rise to many isolated "bubble universes."

As for our own universe, the inflation has ended and it allows stars and galaxies to form. Our universe is just a small bubble in a vast ocean of space. Some regions of the ocean of space are still inflating and it contains many other bubbles like ours. In some of these bubble universes, it is important to take note that the laws of physics and fundamental constants might be different than in ours. This makes some universes peculiar places indeed!

The Hypothesis of Parallel Universes

Steinhardt and Turok (2007) have proposed their hypothesis explaining that parallel universes (or “braneworlds”) exist beyond the reach of our own universe (see Figure 1). The idea arising from the string theory has come from the possibility that there are many more dimensions to our current world than just the 3-D space (length, breadth and height) and the dimension of time that we know today. Steinhardt and Turok (2007) argued that besides our own three-dimensional “brane” of space, there are also other three-dimensional branes floating in a higher-dimensional space unbeknownst to us. In other words, the universe, where our Earth is located, happens to be one of potentially numerous ‘slabs’ floating in a higher-dimensional space (Greene, 2011). According to this hypothesis, these brane universes are not always parallel to each other or out of reach. They might just slam into each other and, hence, causing repeated big bangs that reset the universes all over again.

Figure 1. Parallel universes ...

The Hypothesis of Daughter Universes

Another way to explain the possibility of the existence of multiverses is to turn to the theory of quantum mechanics that delves on the tiny world of subatomic particles. Here the quantum mechanics depicts “the world in terms of probabilities, rather than definite outcomes ... the mathematics of this theory might suggest ... all possible outcomes of a situation do occur ... in their own separate universes” (Moskowitz, 2012, para.11). It is like, as what Moskowitz (2012) has attempted to explain, “if you reach a crossroads where you can go right or left, the present universe gives rise to two daughter universes: one in which you go right, and one in which you go left” (para.11).

According to Greene (2011), in each universe, there are daughter universes: a copy of one universe that you witness or another copy of universe that you see as an outcome, and that there exists more than our reality alone. In fact, Greene (2011) has gone on to discuss nine types of parallel universes or worlds: quilted multiverse, inflationary multiverse, brane multiverse, cyclic multiverse, landscape multiverse, quantum multiverse, holographic multiverse, simulated multiverse and ultimate multiverse. For example, the quilted multiverse is an infinite universe that repeats itself across space and hence, yields parallel worlds, resembling like a quilt. It is not within the scope of this paper to discuss further on this specific topic of interest and readers interested to know more should read Greene (2011) (listed in the References).

The Hypothesis of Mathematical Universes

It is still debatable “whether mathematics is simply a useful tool for describing the universe, or whether mathematics itself is the fundamental reality, and our observations of the universe are just imperfect

perceptions of its true mathematical nature” (Moskowitz, 2012, para.13). In other words, there are two ways of looking at our universe or world. As Moskowitz (2012) has pointed out that “[I]f the latter is the case ... the particular mathematical structure² that makes up our universe isn't the only option ... in fact all possible mathematical structures exist as their own separate universes” (para.13). This means that such a universe or world can exist independently of us or continue to exist without us.

FROM MULTIVERSE/MULTIWORLD TO METAWORLD

So much have been discussed about the multiverse/multiworld, we now turn to talk about the concept of metaworld. What is this term *metaworld*? Roloff (1973) has described it as worlds within worlds whose reality is primarily in the mind. Chia (1996) has defined it as “a place where humans co-exist with creatures of myths and legends – giants and dragons and trolls and dwarves and elves – and where heroes or heroines with magic talismans save the world from the dark forces of evil” (p.14).

In other words, a metaworld is only real within the mental boundaries of mind. In the recreational reading, the existence of such realms can be readily accepted by most readers without an issue of doubt or disbelief. In spite “of how strange or remote it seems to be, readers should be sufficiently convinced that a metaworld really exists: they must believe in it – they need to suspend their disbelief” (Chia, 1991, p.22).

Doyle (1912)

Huxley (1932)

Baum (1914)

Chia (1996) has identified two types of metaworld. The first metaworld deals with improbabilities (i.e., not likely but can possibly happen), and the second metaworld deals with impossibilities (i.e., not possible and can never happen). The former one, according to Chia (1996), includes Conan Doyle's *Lost World* (1912) and Aldous Huxley's *Brave New World* (1932). The latter draws on Frank Baum's *Land of Oz* (1914) and Lewis Carroll's *Wonderland* in *Alice in the Wonderland* (1865), where anything can happen at any time and has no premises to condition the rest of the story. In this latter metaworld, Chia (1996) provides examples such as a carpet that can fly, a frog turns into a handsome prince, a rabbit carries a watch in its waistcoat pocket, a witch flies on her broomstick. There are no maxims, physical or moral, to govern this metaworld. It is an *amora polymorphous* world of a naïve child.

² According to Max Tegmark of MIT (cted in Moskowitz, 2012), a mathematical structure is something that is completely independent of our human baggage and it can exist independently of us and would continue to exist without us.

It is this second metaworld that seems to agree with the hypothesis of bubble universes/worlds which has postulated that the laws of physics and fundamental constants might be different than in our universe/worlds. It is, therefore, not surprising to note that if indeed this hypothesis stands and explains why some universes are peculiar places, then it can also be applied to explain the peculiarity of the metaworld of impossibilities.

For instance, in *The Lion, the Witch and the Wardrobe* (Lewis, 1950), the four Pevensie children – Peter, Susan, Edmund and Lucy – entered Narnia through the wardrobe which serves as a portal linking our world to the other. In that metaworld of Narnia, the dimension of time runs differently from ours here. The four Pevensie children stayed in Narnia and grew up into young adults as Narnian kings and queens. However, when they returned to their world (or this world of ours since they are supposedly from our world and lived in our world during World War II), they got back to their respective original ages when they first entered Narnia. In other words, the time remains the same here in this primary reality, i.e., the difference between the time here and in Narnia is negligible. This possibility can be explained with the hypothesis of parallel universes (or “braneworlds”) that exist beyond our own universe as postulated by Steinhardt and Turok (2007).

Besides our own three-dimensional “brane” of space, there are also other three-dimensional branes, such as Narnia, floating in a higher-dimensional space unbeknownst to us except, of course, the four Pevensie children and the retired professor in whose house they stayed.

Lewis (1950)

Lewis (1955)

Lewis (1956)

In another book *The Magician's Nephew* (Lewis, 1955), the author described Narnia and our middle-age world as two of the many worlds in a multiverse that changes as some new worlds are born while other aging worlds die. Interestingly, the hypothesis of parallel universes explains how these metaworlds (braneworlds) might just crash into each other and cause repeated “big bangs” that end one world and start another one, thereby, resetting the worlds all over again. In the seventh and final book *The Final Battle* (Lewis, 1956), the ancient kings and queens of Narnia, including all its inhabitants gather outside the barn, bear witness to the end of the Narnian world and also to be judged by Aslan. Only those faithful to Aslan can enter Aslan's Country (a parallel metaworld to the metaworld of Narnia but at higher dimensional space or, perhaps, it is more like a meta-metaworld). Others who have opposed or deserted Aslan perish together with the old Narnian world which freezes as Father Time puts out the sun and the moon. Peter the High

King of the old Narnia closes the door behind him following Aslan's lead into the new Narnia as the Lion instructs them to go further into the one true Narnia.

From 3-D Metaworld to 2-D Metaworld

As we move to another series of fictive world *Malice* (Wooding, 2009), here is another metaworld that is somehow linked to our "real" world, where the characters such as Luke, Seth and Kady resided (more like in a metaworld that mirrors ours) until they decided to enter the other world. Unlike most of the known metaworlds such as Narnia, the Land of Oz and the Wonderland of Alice, *Malice* is a 2-D metaworld that exists at a lower dimensional space than our 3-D world within the comic or graphic novel. It is an example of a flatland.

According to Chris Wooding, the author of the duology consisting of *Malice* (Wooding, 2009) and *Havoc* (Wooding, 2010), his reason for writing a book in combination with graphic novel (or comic), where sections of text give way to sections of comic art and back again, is his personal challenge to make it more than a gimmick, so that the comic sections were an integral part of the story. The author explains in his web blog, "I got (a)round that by making it a book about a comic, and the rest fell into place. In *Malice*, the comic sections represent parts of the published comic, and so anyone in the real world – good guys and bad guys – can read them and pick up information about what's going on with the kids trapped inside Tall Jake's world."

Wooding (2009)

Wooding (2010)

Malice was the first fantasy Chris Wooding ever wrote that begins in the "real" world (the word "real", correctly used, is referring to the *Malice* fictive world that mirrors this real world), as "opposed to starting in a fantastical one and staying there" (Wooding, 2009, para.4). The author was very keen that *Malice* "would be pinned to reality as well as fantasy, to keep it grounded ... [S]o I came up with parallel stories, one playing out in the real world and one inside the wild world of *Malice*" (Wooding, 2009, para.4). This is an interplay between the channel of imagination from our real world into the world of fantasy (metaworld) and the channel of verisimilitude from the metaworld returning to our real world (Chia, 1991).

Exploring the 2-D Metaworld of *Malice*

Malice is an interesting metaworld or 2-dimensional flatland, where everyone becomes a part of some comic or graphic novel ... as Kady (one of the supporting protagonists) "looked up at him (Seth), puzzlement and horror on her face. 'The boy in this comic ... it's Luke (classmate of Seth and Kady).'"

(Wooding, 2009, p.64). It is not surprising for the main protagonist, Seth, and also us the readers, to exclaim in disbelief, "This couldn't be real, it just wasn't logical, it must be a hallucination. Maybe he was living an elaborate dream. Maybe he's been hypnotized and this was all someone's idea of a joke." (Wooding, 2009, p.115).

In the comic flatland (a 2-D metaworld), so unlike many fictive metaworlds that we know, "stories weren't complete stories, but rather scenes from different parts of Malice that restlessly flicked back and forth. Sometimes they just showed random incidents, other times they would follow a kid in peril and then abruptly change to something else, as if the artist had got bored" (Wooding, 2009, p.155).

A tour around Malice

If you could actually visit Malice, that's going to be an unforgettable experience as what Seth has described as "terrifying and wonderful. Some would look at it and call it a nightmare, but ... (others like Seth) saw a frontier, the only New World ... The Earth had been explored, mapped, tamed. The chances of getting off the planet within his (Seth's) lifetime were virtually zero" (Wooding, 2009, p.362).

Wooding (2009) has provided a brief description of Malice and most of the times through the eyes of Seth: "The world of Malice spread out beneath a cloudy, sorrowful sky. There was a distant city, a labyrinth and a colossal cemetery ... the Clock Tower standing on the side of the valley, and strange birds winging alongside the train" (p.225). Malice is more than just a *metaland*; it is a *living* land and "[T]he way Malic works, it's kind of like there's an eye or something. And this eye, it keeps looking at different things. Something you see what's happening to some kid in the Deadhouse, and it looks like he's about to make it out, but then suddenly the comic is showing you some other kid in the Labyrinth who you've never seen before. And you never find out what happened to the Deadhouse kid" (Wooding, 2009, p.231).

Portal to Malice

There are a few ways of getting to Malice. The first way was what most hormone-ravaging teenage boys dare each other to do: conducting some kind of an occult ritual that requires them to chant the name of Tall Jake (a tall, dark figure – the antagonist in Malice) six times to take them away ... and before they realized what had happened ... they were whisked out of this world into Malice!

Another way was taking a train from this world to Malice ... only if you have a special ticket to get there and to return. There are "two types of ticket: black and white. A black ticket buys you one trip anywhere within Malice. To a different domain, say. A white ticket buys you one trip anywhere at all. Even back home, if that's what you want" (Wooding, 2009, p.121).

Kady, who wanted to save Seth and bring him out of Malice, entered the metaworld by train. This is what Kady experienced: "She got to her feet, picked up her pack and went through the dividing door into the carriage. It was empty except for a young couple who had both fallen asleep. She stood in the aisle ... still standing there when the train thundered into a tunnel. The lights flickered, sputtered, and went dark for an instant. When they came back up, Kady wasn't on the same train ... The sleeping couple was gone. The chairs had been replaced by benches of coiled metal. Overhead lights glowed inside cages, and the windows were like the portholes of a ship. The noise was different, the smell was different, the *feel* was different. And yet somewhere familiar ... She was in Malice" (Wooding, 2009, p.289).

Places in Malice

Depending on how you look at Malice, it could be quite a vast metaworld linking one place to another such as Menagerie and the Oubliette, where the way out of the place was to go downward ... to get to the bottom ... down, to Skarla, to the exit" (Wooding, 2009, p.317). To travel between these places, the best mode of transport is the train in Malice.

Wooding (2009) has described Menagerie as a wonderland: "A glittering carnival of glass and chrome, polished surfaces and bright colors. There were carousels with strange beasts that writhed and gaped as they moved. There were elaborate buildings like giant doll's houses, with gaudy figures acting out silent scenes within. A shiny train, its front end fashioned into a grinning face, chugged along upside down on an aerial track. The metal boughs of mechanical trees swayed in a small clockwork park, blown by an imaginary wind" (p.160). There in Menagerie was the Clock Tower where the scary Timekeeper stayed and he controlled the time for the train to arrive and/or depart. After their narrow escape from being viciously attacked by the Timekeeper, Justin (someone Seth had befriended in Malice) told Seth that "[T]he Clock Tower in Menagerie was bad. The Oubliette is worse" (Wooding, 2009, p.220).

The land where the Oubliette situated was colossally dark (Wooding, 2009, p.304) and damp chill (Wooding, 2009, p.330). It was also a treacherous place to explore because nobody knew where danger was lurking in the dark. They had to go to the Oubliette to find Skarla (the Queen of cats), whom they assumed knew how to defeat Tall Jake and his gang, and also to get out of Malice, but "[S]he lives at the bottom of the Oubliette" (Wooding, 2009, p.219). It was also at Skarla's place where Seth and his friends could exit from Malice.

Among the deserted buildings in the Oubliette that Seth, Kady and Justin explored was a sacred place, probably a temple or church of some sort, but the place "had been horribly defiled. Spirally pillars of what looked like black and purple glass rose up from the smooth floor, but most of them were broken and lay in pieces. Elaborate alcoves had once sheltered statues, all had been tipped and smashed" (Wooding, 2009, p.320).

Beyond Malice

While exploring the temple, Seth, Kady and Justin came to "[T]he only part of the chamber that seemed undamaged was in the center of the room. It was a life-size statue of a woman holding an ornate bow. She was standing on a hexagonal pedestal with the bow tilted upwards towards the ceiling, as if aiming at something overhead. ... They followed her gaze upwards. The roof of the chamber couldn't be seen. Instead, it was claimed by darkness, and speckled with stars. There were bright nebulae up there, colorful clouds of interstellar gas, distant galaxies and star nurseries. It was a universe, impossibly far and yet close enough that it seemed they could have climbed one of the unbroken pillars and brushed it with outstretched fingers" (Wooding, 2009, p320-321).

Interestingly, the three characters were able to see nebulae, galaxies and star nurseries that spread across the dark sky from the dilapidated temple in the Oubliette. Malice is, therefore, not just a 2-D metaworld seen in comic but also a metaworld that links to the universe that we know. If the universe as described by Wooding is not referring to the same universe of ours, then it could just be a meta-universe (or a meta-metaworld of ours but a metaworld of Malice) on the other side of ours (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. The real world and the meta-metaworld as seen from metaworld

Inhabitants of Malice

Unlike the terrifying Chitters – machines that resembled noisy monkeys – that went hunting for human children to suck their lives out of their bodies in Malice, the inhabitants in Menagerie were more amazing. “Many were animals, or creatures that resembled animals. Others were unlike anything ... ever seen. But all of them had been built, all made of cogs and gears and joints, unimaginably complex” (Wooding, 2009, pp.160-161) and there were also “clockwise mosquitoes that were huge as a cat” and “clockwork birds that are *just too heavy to fly*” *but they could fly!* It defiles the laws of physics that we know here.

Everywhere in the Oubliette were what Wooding (2009) called them *gnawls*: “draped over the rubble, lazing on ledges, sleeping on the edge of the waterway like pale six-legged crocodiles. The clamor of their tails was deafening” (p.238).

There were also mechanical plants called *glowglobes* – “curious plants that grow around the pillars in the train station in the Oubliette (Wooding, 2009, p.223). These glowglobes resembled light balls and they could be used as torchlights but their light span did not last too long

Law of physics in Malice

As has been already explained in the hypothesis of bubble universes, the laws of physics and fundamental constants in a metaworld might be different than in ours, making that world a peculiar place to us. For example, it is “hard to gauge the velocity” (Wooding, 2009, p.239) of a train travelling in Malice. Seth has also quickly realized it, too: “Malice had new rules. Rules he (She) didn’t know” (Wooding, 2009, p.131). Once in a different world, Seth has “to stop thinking about the world outside (i.e., our world or his world). That won’t be his (Seth’s) problem any more. *This place (Malice) was his problem. This place, this real place.*” (Wooding, 2009, p.131). Hence, to survive in totally unknown world (metaworld), one has to “[L]earn the world. Then you can beat it” (Wooding, 2009, p.131) a wise advice offered to Seth by Justin (another boy who has been in Malice far longer than Seth).

Communication between our world and Malice

Communicating between our world and another metaworld (in this case, the metaworld of Malice) is also totally impossible. “The words are just gibberish. Whenever they try to talk to anyone on the outside, or give anything really important away about Malice, the words in the speech bubble (as seen in comics) get scrambled” (Wooding, 2009, p.232). It seems like there is some kind of an invisible chasm between the two worlds such that there is absolutely no way to communicate directly between them.

CONCLUSION

Understanding metaworlds apart from our real world can get readers to think beyond their normal daily encounters and expectations of what should be. Real or unreal, possible or impossible, probable or improbable, things or events that happen in a metaworld also allows readers to use their mind-eye to see, perceive or experience things differently. This taps on their higher order thinking skills (i.e., creative, disruptive-innovative and imaginative) to learn how the characters in *Malice* went about overcoming obstacles while on their dangerous mission to defeat Tall Jake and getting others out of that 2-D metaworld.

On this side of reality, our world could be just a hologram or a holographic world (or *holographoworld* if I might term it) where our 3-D world may actually include one or more 2-D worlds or flatlands that one may call it, like in the case of a graphic novel or comic such as *Malice* or *Havoc*. Perhaps in the not-too-distant future, theoretical physicists may make new discoveries to show that our world is indeed a kind of hologram where 2-D worlds or flatworlds are subsets of ours. Currently, we do not know for sure but should a hidden portal between our world and the other 2-D worlds be found to exist somewhere in the space between or among the spaces, then *Malice* and the places that joined to it is every child's nightmare that has become scarily *real*!

References

- Baum, F. (1914). *Land of Oz*. Chicago, IL: Reilly and Lee.
- Carroll, L. (1865). *Alice in the wonderland*. London, UK: Macmilian.
- Chia, N.K.H. (1991). The imaginative creation of metaworlds in the recreational reading process. *Education Today*, 41(3), 22-25.
- Chia, N.K.H. (1996, November). The neverland of fantasy. *The Family Tree*, Nov/Dec issue, 14.
- Deutsch, D. (2011). *The beginning of infinity*. NY: Viking Press.
- Doyle, C. (1912). *The lost world*. London, UK: Houghton and Stoughton.
- Greene, B. (2011). *The hidden reality: Parallel universes and the deep laws of the cosmos*. NY: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Huxley, A. (1932). *Brave new world*. London, UK: Chatto and Windus.
- James, W. (1895). *The will to believe*, as cited in Oxford English Dictionary (2003), a new entry for "multiverse"; also James, W. (1895 October). Is life worth living? *International Journal of Ethics*, 6, p.10.
- Lewis, C.S. (1950). *The lion, the witch and the wardrobe*. London, UK: Geoffrey Bles.
- Lewis, C.S. (1955). *The magician's nephew*. London, UK: Bodley Head.
- Lewis, C.S. (1956). *The last battle*. London, UK: Bodley Head.
- Moskowitz, C. (2012). *5 reasons why we may live in a metaverse*. Retrieved [online] from: <http://www.space.com/18811-multiple-universes-5-theories.html>
- Roloff, L.H. (1973). *The perception and evocation of literature*. Chicago, IL: Scott and Foreman.
- Steinhardt, P.J., & Turoke, N. (2007). *Endless universe: Beyond the big bang*. NY: Doubleday Broadway.
- Vilenkin, A. (1983). Birth of inflationary universes. *Physical Review D*, 27, 2848.
- Wooding, C. (2009). *Malice*. London, UK: Scholastic.
- Wooding, C. (2010). *Havoc*. London, UK: Scholastic.

About the Author

Dr Noel KH Chia gained his Diploma in Writing under the tutelage of the late British author, John O'Toole, at the London School of Writing in 1985. Thereafter, he wrote and published short stories for children in

children's periodicals such as D'Light, Funland and Student Literature. Later, he went on to study Child's Literature as a minor at Edith Cown University, Perth, Western Australia. In 2010, he was awarded the Lee Kong Chian Research Fellowship to do a study tracing the historical development of the growth of imagination in Singapore children's literature in English 1965-2005 at the Lee Kong Chian Reference Library, National Library Board, Singapore.

